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Autonomous Network Management for 5G and Beyond Services and Vertical Applications: Case Studies

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Intelligent network slicing with online learning capabilities

- Advanced network slicing, substantially optimized for the targeted **Industry 4.0** use cases (Factory of Future etc.).
- **Maximized usage of radio resources** and thus network capacity with QoS warranty.
- **Optimised trade-off** of performance and cost-efficiency.
- **E2E intent-based, voice-controlled network slice management and orchestration** for various use cases.
- **Online learning capabilities** based on reinforcement deep learning.

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Thank you very much!